

Bulk-Driven Rail-to-Rail Comparator with V_{DD} of 0.25 V in 65 nm CMOS Technology

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Abstract—This paper addresses the design and verification of a voltage comparator of novel topology, implemented in a 65 nm general-purpose CMOS technology. The proposed circuit combines a bulk-driven transistor approach with so-called *current-mode* operation, which enables truly promising ultra-low-voltage performance. Design verification has been carried out using Monte-Carlo simulations across an industrial temperature range from $T = -20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $T = 85\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, as well as through simulations across all relevant process-voltage-temperature (PVT) corners. The proposed topology demonstrates the ability to operate correctly with V_{DD} as low as 250 mV with rail-to-rail input voltage range. The comparator can achieve a very low input offset voltage *without* trimming or digital calibration, at the cost of increased silicon area consumption. However, the presented topology can be easily modified to implement various trimming methods, if required.

Index Terms—Bulk-Driven, CMOS technology, Rail-to-Rail, Ultra Low-Voltage, Ultra Low-Power

I. INTRODUCTION

The field of ultra-low-voltage and ultra-low-power (ULV and ULP) integrated circuit design has seen rapid advancements, driven by the rise of technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), energy harvesting, and more [1]. Analog and mixed-signal circuit design in nanoscale CMOS fabrication processes (such as 65 nm) has become increasingly dependent on circuit trimming (e.g. by laser or one-time programmable fuses), digital calibration, or analog-to-digital conversion. This shift is primarily due to increased process and lithography variations, aging effects, reduced dynamic voltage headroom, and other factors [2].

The combination of low power supply voltages and increased process-related effects in nanoscale CMOS technologies has made the analog and mixed-signal IC design challenging, even for experienced designers. Integrated systems-on-chip (SoCs) often require the use of non-standard design techniques and/or circuit topologies, along with the aforementioned post-process trimming or digital calibration. The bulk-driven (BD) IC design approach is a prime example of an unconventional application of nanoscale MOS transistors. Although, this methodology has been silicon-proven multiple times, its adoption and impact remain relatively limited.

Nevertheless, it has the potential to deliver promising results and novel circuit solutions. Several analog and mixed-signal bulk-driven circuits have been proposed, including operational amplifiers, charge pumps, fully differential difference amplifiers, and voltage comparators, along with novel methods for their calibration and digital trimming in the bulk-driven domain [3]–[5].

Building upon our previous research on bulk-driven circuit design in a 130 nm CMOS process, we propose a novel voltage comparator circuit topology capable of rail-to-rail input voltage processing and operating with a power supply voltage as low as $V_{DD} = 0.25\text{ V}$ [6], [7]. Earlier comparator designs were originally devised for higher supply voltages. However, the presented topology shows tremendous potential for further V_{DD} reduction. The *theoretical* limit for the minimum supply voltage is determined by two saturation voltages under given operating conditions, yielding approximately $2 \cdot V_{DS_{sat}} \approx 220\text{ mV}$ at room temperature.

Given the low power supply voltage, the employed MOS devices are expected to operate in the weak inversion (or subthreshold region), where transconductance efficiency is highest, saturation voltages are lowest, intrinsic gain is maximized, and DC mismatch is minimized [8]. On the downside, all time- and frequency-related circuit parameters are reduced due to the use of large transistors with high gate capacitances and low current levels.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 discusses the comparator design in detail, including the transistor-level schematic, small-signal analysis, and design considerations for the analog core. Section 3 focuses on the digital part of the design, which generates the final decision output. This section also explores the possible integration of digital trimming and the modifications required to support it. Section 4 presents key verification results obtained from a thorough evaluation of the circuit's parameters. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper stating the most important contributions of the presented work along with a discussion of our future research plans and directions.

Fig. 1. The schematic diagram of analog core.

II. THE PROPOSED COMPARATOR TOPOLOGY

A. Novel Analog Core for $V_{DD} = 0.25 V$

The proposed analog core represents the next step in our research and development of ultra-low-voltage and ultra-low-power analog/mixed-signal IC design. Building on our previous work, we propose the topology with increased voltage gain, which required adding two extra current-drawing branches. The resulting topology is shown in Fig. 1. The integer M denotes the device multiplier, which was set to $M = 8$ in our implementation.

The analog core is fully symmetrical, so we will describe only its left-hand side. Devices M_{IN+} and $M1$ form the input circuit branch, comprising a diode that further biases a current mirror system and a bulk-driven current source controlled by the actual comparator input voltage. This voltage regulates the current flow through the input branch with a negative slope. As the input potential increases, the potential at node A (green color) rises as well. A major advantage of the proposed solution is that the input voltage can swing across full rail-to-rail range. The main drawback is the circuit's inherent negative feedback. Unfortunately, the voltage gain at node A is less than 0 dB, as shown in Eq. 1, which defines the small-signal voltage gain.

$$A_{V_A} = \frac{g_{mbs_{MIN+}}}{g_{mbs_{MIN+}} + g_{m_{MIN+}} + g_{m1} + g_{ds_{MIN+}} + g_{ds1}} \quad (1)$$

The second branch consists of transistors $M2$ and $M5$, forming a classic PMOS common-source amplifier with a diode-connected load and output node B. The third node of interest, node C, is cross-coupled and derives its voltage gain from the NMOS common-source amplifier $M6$ with current source $M9$ as its load. Note that transistor $M9$ is biased from the right-hand side of the circuit, this is where the differential voltage emerges. The voltage gain from node A to node C is defined by Eq. 2. The first fraction corresponds to the gain from node A to node B, and the second to the gain from node B to node C.

$$A_{V_C} = \frac{g_{m2}}{g_{m5} + g_{ds2} + g_{ds5}} \cdot \frac{g_{m6}}{g_{ds6} + g_{ds9}} \quad (2)$$

The small-signal voltages at nodes A and C drive the output devices $M4$ and $M7$, providing the amplified differential voltage. The analytical expression is given in Eq. 3.

$$A_{V_{diff}} = A_{V_A} \cdot \frac{g_{m4} + g_{m7} \cdot A_{V_C}}{g_{ds4} + g_{ds7}} \quad (3)$$

As seen above, the attenuation at node A is compensated by the gain at node C and the transconductance of the output transistors. All devices must be laid out in symmetrical and regular patterns with an emphasis on device matching. In this case, metallization parasitics do not significantly affect circuit performance, so the use of additional vias and complex routing is acceptable.

B. Controlling and Output Logic

The differential voltage from the analog core is processed by the output logic block, which generates the final binary decision, as shown in Fig. 2. This block was described using SystemVerilog HDL and synthesized as purely combinational logic using only inverters and gates with two single-bit inputs. This approach is favorable at low supply voltages, as these standard cells do not stack more than three transistors between the supply rails. The resulting circuit has also been verified by *analog* simulations across the respective PVT corners.

Fig. 2. Controlling digital block with output latch.

The outputs PU and PD control the pull-up and pull-down transistors (not shown in the schematics) used to tie-off circuit nodes in the analog core when the comparator is disabled by setting $EN = 0$.

We also investigated the possibility of implementing the control block using pass-transistor logic. However, the final logic circuit used the same number of transistors and exhibited even higher power consumption than classic static CMOS logic. The output latch and final inverter were custom-designed to meet the drive requirements for the given supply voltage and capacitive load. The latching circuit, composed of transistors $M1$ through $M4$, provides steeper transfer characteristics and therefore improves the noise margin.

C. Digital Trimming

The final comparator design, which is to be submitted to the foundry for fabrication at this stage, is considered a proof of concept. Therefore, we designed the proposed topology to be as robust as *reasonably* possible. This includes using fairly large devices in the analog core to reduce the impact of random process variations that cause input offset voltage.

The next logical step is to design a comparator that supports digital trimming or calibration. Based on the results of our small-signal analysis, we can safely assume that fine-tuning devices M_{IN+} , $M4$, and $M7$ (and their symmetrical counterparts) should suffice to achieve minimal input offset voltage or the desired voltage gain.

In our project, the trimming code is provided externally by a microcontroller present on the testing PCB. Our prototype ASIC includes an SPI bus interface and a 1-byte-wide register map. The design has also been written in SystemVerilog and synthesized with a focus on low power consumption. The trimming section of each analog circuit block is connected to the register map at specific map address, enabling effective and precise trimming and fine-tuning via embedded C or higher-level languages (e.g. Python, MATLAB, etc.) [9]. Once the trimming codes for the analog IC domain are determined and fixed, programming the entire register map requires exactly 1,032 clock cycles, which, at $f_{SCLK} = 1\text{ MHz}$, takes approximately 1 *ms*.

III. POST-LAYOUT SIMULATION RESULTS

The proposed circuit design underwent rigorous verification using Monte-Carlo and PVT corner simulations with back-annotated layout parasitics. The results of the DC transfer analysis under all PVT corners are shown in Fig. 3. As shown, the proposed comparator produces the correct output across all PVT corners, with the reference placed at the midpoint of the voltage range and 5 *mV* from both rail potentials, in order to verify the rail-to-rail feature.

The same conditions were applied in our power analysis. The waveforms of worst-case supply current drawn by the proposed comparator under all PVT corners are shown in Fig. 4. As expected, the highest power consumption occurs at high operating temperatures and in the FF process corner. A significant portion of the overall consumption at this temperature can be attributed to leakage currents of large MOS devices. However, the average current consumption in nominal conditions is approximately $I_{DD} = 210\text{ nA}$, which makes it $P_{DD} = 53\text{ nW}$.

Fig. 3. DC transfer characteristics in various PVT conditions.

Fig. 4. The worst-case supply current in various PVT conditions.

The results of the input offset analysis are shown in Fig. 5. We set the *transient* simulation with central and corner voltage levels as a reference and the “swept” voltage was modeled as one period of a triangle waveform. The period was of very high value (e.g. $T = 10\text{ s}$) in order to mitigate the transient delays within the design. This method yields two offset values per simulation - one for the rising output edge and one for the falling edge. We performed 500 iterations for each reference and temperature combination, resulting in a total of 4500 offset values. The mean and standard deviation values of the histogram indicate an acceptable input offset voltage, less than 1 *mV* and 1.23 *mV*, respectively. The offset could be further minimized through digital trimming made available by SPI interface and register map.

A crucial parameter in our design is power consumption, which must not exceed a maximum value of $P_{DD} = 1\text{ μW}$. The results of the power analysis are shown in Fig. 6. Both comparator inputs were grounded to establish worst-case voltage conditions, and 500 Monte-Carlo iterations were performed for each temperature corner.

Fig. 5. MC results of input offset in all temperature corners.

It is clear that the power consumption remains below 300 nW , even under the worst-case voltage and temperature scenarios, as well as with random process variations and device mismatch.

Regarding the dynamics of the presented design, the severely limited power supply voltage restricts the maximum frequency to kHz range. For instance, under nominal conditions, the maximum frequency achieved was only $f_{MAX} = 30 \text{ kHz}$.

Fig. 6. MC results of power consumption in worst-case voltage conditions.

IV. CONCLUSION

The proposed paper presents a robust design of a novel voltage comparator topology that ensures reliable operation across the industrial temperature range, with an ultra-low supply voltage of $V_{DD} = 0.25 \text{ V}$. The design has been thoroughly validated through simulations and back-annotated layout parasitics, confirming correct behavior and promising performance under random process variations, device mismatch, and all PVT scenarios. The comparator supports full rail-to-rail input voltage processing and exhibits a very low input offset voltage. At the specified supply voltage, the power consumption remains safely within the nanowatt range. Notably, the power consumption under nominal conditions is just $P_{DD} = 53 \text{ nW}$, which is truly remarkable. The maximum frequency can be expected in the range of kHz due to severely limited supply voltage.

Our future plans include laboratory measurements of the prototype chips confirming the correct performance in all temperature conditions, as well as finding the *real* minimal power supply voltage, the presented circuit can reliably work with.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported in part by the Slovak Research and Development Agency under grant APVV-23-0071 and the Ministry of Education, Research, Development and Youth of the Slovak Republic under grants VEGA 1/0572/25 and VEGA 1/0614/24. This research was done in the framework of "Matching" Grant No.09101-03-V04-00030 from Recovery and Resilience Plan for the Slovak Republic.

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